

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14914698

Mathematical Modelling of Influenza A/H1N1 2009 Epidemics and Pandemics using Euler Method.

*Nasiru Magaji & Sauda Sanni

Department of Mathematics
Federal College Education, P.M.B 1021, Gidan Madi Sokoto State, Nigeria

*Email: nasiroumagajee@gmail.com
Mobile No: 09060804433, 070854043485.

ABSTRACT

Mathematical model can be used for the development and implementation of infection control policy to fight pandemics and epidemic of contagious viral disease to identify the spread of infectious disease in a community and understand infectious dynamics; any time an outbreak of communicable disease occurs, to forecast characteristics of the outbreak, models can be used. For example, size and duration of the outbreak to build epidemic scenarios and model the impact of possible interventions. Mathematical modelling helps in guidance to control strategies and policy decisions. Models can also be useful in estimating important epidemiological parameters from the outbreak and data also be used for the preparedness and moderation planning of the future epidemics retrospective analysis in support of policy development. The objectives of this work is to describe a mathematical model that can model the transmission of influenza A/H1N1 virus using Euler method and shows that the disease dies out if the basic reproductive number $R_0 < 1$ while the diseases may be come epidemic if $R_0 > 1$. At end we run some numerical simulation to elaborate the result. Here, we modelled the influenza virus epidemics and pandemics of A/N1N1 2009 using Euler techniques We find out that the disease eradicate after the first hundred days which shows clear similarities with the result obtained by weekly estimated incident pandemics A/H1N1 cases and confirmed deaths in England and concluded that infectious cases reach it maximum peak of 10% within one hundred days (100 days) before the diseases die out thereafter. We concluded that influenza virus can be modelled by applying the Euler techniques to SEIR model. We also found out that the disease vanishes after one hundred days which is similar to the result obtained of weekly estimated incidence of pandemics A/H1N1 2009 England influenza virus outbreak.

Keywords: influenza A/H1N1 virus, transmission, mathematical model

INTRODUCTION

FLU: Normally known as influenza is an infectious disease stimulates by the influenza the virus. Symptoms vary from mild to severe. Symptoms usually include: Running nose, a high fever, and sore throat, and muscle pain, headache, coughing and feeling tired (Rose *et al.*, 2014). These typical symptoms star two days after the exposure to the virus and mostly last less than a week. Influenza complication comprises viral pneumonia, secondary pneumonia, sinus infection, and deterioration of preceding health problem such as heart failure and asthma. Three categories of influenza affecting people include, normally, the virus spread through the air from coughs or sneezes. Having contacts with the contaminated surface by virus and then touching the mouth or eyes can lead to the spread of the virus. An infectious

person can infect others both before and during the sick (Rose *et al.*, 2014). Washing of hand regularly bring down the risk of infection because soap make the virus to become inactive. Three or four classis of influenza can effectively be vaccinated against. LAIV is made usually at end or beginning of every year, but done once every year. Influenza being an old disease it continues to pose a new treat every year. It brings more than 2000 deaths annually in Canada and more 36,000 deaths in the US. Usually the strains that go around are similar to the one that have been circulating in the previous years, and many people may have some remains of immunity (Rose *et al.*, 2014).

Modelling Problem

Viral airways diseases as a result of flu pose extreme health problems to humans, basically affecting pupil of any age particularly those with hidden therapeutic conditions. Pandemics and regular flue infections are public health danger with significant morbidity and mortality worldwide. Furthermore, research has shown that children were most affected by influenza. Rate of sickness are noteworthy among children, and influenza are viruses that are responsible for significant health and economic burden. Especially in young children, hospitalization from influenza and its complication are similar to those seen among the elderly population (Rose *et al.*, 2014). About 40% of the all influenza 24% of outpatient visits 10% of hospitalization days and 27% of working days lost due to influenza are caused by childhood influenza (Rose *et al.*, 2014). In addition children are the major vector of influenza transmission within house hold and communities, resulting in additional burden of disease from secondary transmission of influenza .Immunization provides an effective and efficient tool to control the spread of influenza. Hence influenza vaccination is widely recommended by international health organization, mostly targeting the elderly population and people with underlying chronic condition (Rose *et al.*, 2014). In 2012 the WHO Strategic Advisory Group of Experts on immunization (SAGE) suggest that children up to five 5 years of age should consider as a targeting group for annual influenza vaccination (Rose *et al.*, 2014).Several national explanations suggest that yearly influenza vaccination for children (Rose *et al.*, 2014). For example, since 2010, the US Advisory Committee on Immunization practices (ACIP) has recommended yearly influenza immunization for children age six 6 months and above (Rose *et al.*, 2014). The UK'S joint committee on vaccination and immunization (JCV) which propose the UK government on immunization policy recently suggest on enlargement to the recent public influenza vaccination of children ranging from two 2 to less than 17 years (Rose *et al.*, 2014). Nevertheless, in so many countries children do not receive influenza vaccination. In spite of the fact that they are highly at risk for infection and tend to diffuse them via the community (Rose *et al.*, 2014). In Europe, vaccination oppose to the influenza has been mainly based on injectable trivalent inactive influenza vaccines (TIV) supplying systematic immunity particularly in immune competent persons with antecedent contact with virus. In 2012 intra nasally administered live-attenuated influenza vaccine (LAIV) has also become accessible in Europe, giving supper immunological feature and a best protection of children and adolescent teenagers than TIV (Rose *et al.*, 2014). Knowing the manners of influenza transmission and the possible result of it prevention by vaccine is important for physicians, policy makers and patients in order to fully understand the treasure of influenza vaccination. Base on a complex mathematical model of seasonal influenza transmission and prevention (Rose *et al.*, 2014).

Mathematical Epidemics Model (SEIR)

Mathematical model are a simplified representation of how an infection spread across a population over time and generally come in two forms: Stochastic and deterministic models. The first ones, employ randomness, with variable being described by probability distribution (Louzet *al.*, 2010). Here the main focus will be deterministic models which splits the population in to subclasses, and an ODEs (Ordinary differential Equations) with respect to time is formulated for each. The stated variables are determined using parameters and initial conditions. In the SEIR model, the transmission process occurs with initial inoculation with a very small number of pathogens. Then, during a period of time the pathogen reduces rapidly within the host, relatively unchallenged by the immune system. During this stage pathogen abundance is too low for active transmission to other susceptible host, and yet pathogen is present. The time in this stage is very difficult to quantify, since there is no symptomatic features of the disease. It is refers to latent period. Recent preventive and control measure of influenza epidemics is annually

vaccination with trivalent inactivated influenza vaccine (Rose *et al.*, 2014). Routine is advised primarily to person at high risk of influenza similar complications and death, such as elderly above 65 years and patient with the severe health conditions (Rose *et al.*, 2014). Influenza vaccines are, in general, has little effect in elderly, than in younger population groups (Rose *et al.*, 2014). While, for example healthy adult constitute about 70% to 90% of the protective post vaccination antibody titres, achieving the protection-Rate 40%-60% [5, 6]. New vaccine and vaccination approaches are now being put in to consideration, just to improve the efficiency of influenza vaccination in high risk group. This enforces on primary health care workers a task of taking decision of who should be a candidate for an alternative vaccine approach and who should not. The problem is especially emphasizes because of the inconsistency of the report on the outcome of influenza vaccination campaigns. In contrary what may be expected, some report showed that the influenza vaccinations in high risk groups are as effective as in the young control groups [3]

SIMPLE SEIR MODEL

Assumption: 1, every susceptible individual (S) in the community is free of the disease before becoming expose to the disease and inter a latent period. Here birth is very important we can use SEIR model with demography. So here the birth rate μ inters in to the susceptible correspond with new-borns while the corresponding μ going out of the E, I and R compartments is the death rate i.e. μ represent both birth and death rate.

Assumption: 2, we assumed an individual who is expose can be represented by (E)

Assumption: 3, we assume individual become infected (I) after being expose or passing through a latent period.

Assumption: 4, we assumed that every infected individual recovers from the infection and returns to the susceptible class.

Assumption: 5, $1/\sigma$ is the average duration of the latent period

Other Assumption: Are β is the product of the contact rate and the transmission probability and the γ is the recovery rate while σ is the incubation or latent period.

We determine the reproductive ratio of this model. By assuming that $S=1$ so that the entire population is susceptible.

METHODOLOGY

This explains in details the next step in the research process, which is the development of methodology. The methodology involves what you will actually do so as to address the specific objectives and research question you have develop (Newing *et al.*, 2011).

Research is a careful investigation, systematic investigation towards increasing the sum of knowledge (Newing *et al.*, 2011). Research simply involves finding out new ideas through systematics enquiry. Scientific research carried out this through direct observation of ‘real world’ as oppose to research into ideas or texts, as in the humanities also known as (empherical observation). Nevertheless it is not possible to give a single definitive description of research, because it is beyond these broad generalization, even the word systematics can have so many definition in different ways (Newing *et al.*, 2011).

Research strategies centre on the relationship between the data and theory, and more emphasis will be geared toward the question of which come first, is it the theory or data are central to the research design. The two most common research strategies are deduction and induction, which stand for the two ends of a range of possible approaches to research. In deductive research, a specific theory by researcher will come up and hypothesis and designs the data collection process in order to test it (Newing *et al.*, 2011). In inductive research there is no specific hypothesis contrary to deductive research. Instead data collection is guided by a set of broad questions or issues, and the data are used to generate a theory or hypothesis as soon as enough evidence has been collected to reveal what is going on (Newing *et al.*, 2011).

Research can be classified in two different forms these are quantitative and qualitative according to two different stages in research process; data collection and data analysis. Data in form of numbers are refers to Quantitative data. Whereas qualitative data are non-numerical and usually take the form of words or images (Newing *et al.*, 2011).

Quantitative Analysis

This consist the use of descriptive and inferential and since statistics require numbers, it can only be perform on quantitative data or numbers obtained from the qualitative data (Newing *et al.*, 2011).

Qualitative Analysis

Also this include ascertaining, summarizing and synthesising from difference qualitative sources so as to build a narrative account and can be perform on any kind of data, Even though it is commonly associated with qualitative data.

In this research work we collected data from different relevant published journals that adopted different modelling techniques of influenza virus disease during the 2009 pandemic. Various author used different modelling techniques to analyses the influenza virus disease. But in our research work we use Euler method to make a comparative analysis with different methods adopt in the paper. In our work we used quantitative analysis because it involved numerical data to carry out the comparative analysis.

METHOD

The transmission of influenza follows SEIR model (Susceptible –Expose-Infectious-Recovered) dynamics and can be described by the following set of ordinary differential equations ODEs (Althaus, 2014 and louzet *al.*, 2010).

The model can be formulated as follows:

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = \mu - \beta SI - \mu S$$

$$\frac{dE}{dt} = \beta SI - \sigma E - \mu E$$

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = \sigma E - \mu I - \gamma I$$

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = \gamma I - \mu R$$

$$S = \mu - \beta SI - \mu S \Rightarrow S_{n+1} = S_{n+h}(\mu - \beta S_n I_n - \mu S_n)$$

$$E = \beta SI - \sigma E - \mu E \Rightarrow E_{n+1} = E_{n+h}(\beta S_n I_n - \sigma E_n - \mu E_n)$$

$$I = \sigma E - \mu I - \gamma I \Rightarrow I_{n+1} = I_{n+h}(\sigma E_n - \mu I_n - \gamma I_n)$$

$$R = \gamma I - \mu R \Rightarrow R_{n+1} = R_{n+h}(\gamma I_n - \mu R_n)$$

The Euler method gives the following sequence of approximation of the above ordinary differential equations (ODEs). These sequence of approximation will be programme in to excel together with the parameters values obtain in the table 1 below to produce the graph in figure 1 below.

$$t_{n+1} = t_{n+h} \Rightarrow = A5 + \$C\$2$$

$$S_{n+1} = S_{n+h}(\mu - \beta S_n I_n - \mu S_n)$$

$$= B5 + \$C\$2 * (\$E\$1 - \$G\$1 * B5 * D5 + \$E\$1 * B5)$$

$$E_{n+1} = E_{n+h}(\beta S_n I_n - \sigma E_n - \mu E_n)$$

$$= C5 + \$C\$ * (\$G\$1 * B5 * D5 * \$S\$1 * C5)$$

$$I_{n+1} = I_{n+h}(\sigma E_n - \mu I_n - \gamma I_n)$$

$$= D5 + \$I\$2 * (\$I\$1 * C5 - \$E\$1 * D5 - \$K\$1 * D5)$$

$$R_{n+1} = R_{n+h}(\gamma I_n - \mu R_n)$$

$$= E5 + \$C\$2 * (\$K\$1 * D5 - \$E\$1 * E5)$$

With the initial conditions $S(0) > 0$, $E(0) \geq 0$, $I(0) \geq 0$, $R \geq (0)$.

The expression for the basic reproduction number is

$R_0 = \frac{\beta \sigma}{(\gamma + \mu)(\sigma + \mu)}$, this threshold is the product of the contact rate β per unit time, the infectious period adjusts to the population growth of $\frac{1}{\gamma + \mu}$.

Table 1. Parameters used in simple modelling of influenza.

Parameter	Symbol	values	Sources
Transmission rate	β	0.36	
New born babies (birth rate) (day^{-1})	μ	0.00003	Coburn <i>et al.</i> , 2009 Shilet <i>al.</i> , 2009
Recovery rate (day^{-1})	γ	0.2	Shilet <i>al.</i> , 2009 &
Latent period(incubation period) (day^{-1})	σ	0.53	Shilet <i>al.</i> , 2009
Number of Susceptible	S	0.999	
Number of expose people	E	0.0	
Number of infected people	I	0.001	
Number recovered people	R	0.0	

The parameters in the table 1 above used in simple SEIR Model.

Source: Author Figure 1.

X axis (vertical) represent number of people (population size).

Y axis (horizontal) represent the number days.

Numerical solution of SEIR model performed in excel spreadsheet showing the transmission of influenza epidemic and pandemic of A/H1N1 2009 outbreak from (June-November). SEIR represents Susceptible, Expose, Infectious and Recovered respectively.

Prediction From The Model

The basic reproductive number is commonly denoted as R_0 and defines as the number of secondary cases generated by primary infectious case during its entire period of infectiousness in a completely susceptible population. One of the objectives of public health is to minimize this quantity to a number less than one as soon as possible. Therefore when R_0 greater than one is, an epidemic can occur while a basic reproductive number less than one will not sustain an epidemic.

For $R_0 < 1$ the infection should be eliminated. The data in table 1 for influenza indicates that in most facilities γ is 0.2 per day, μ is 0.00003 per day σ is 0.53 per day. Furthermore, the data indicates that is R_0 between 1.6 and 1.8. This implies that β is 0.36 per day. Typical parameter values are given in table 1. The model indicate that after 100 days the disease is eradicated.

The basic reproductive ratio for this model is $R_0 = \frac{\beta\sigma}{(\gamma+\mu)(\sigma+\mu)}$

$$R_0 = \frac{0.36 \times 0.53}{(0.2 \times 0.00003)(0.53 \times 0.00003)}$$

$$R_0 = \frac{0.1908}{(0.200003)(0.530003)}$$

$$R_0 = \frac{0.1908}{0.1060219009}$$

$$R_0 = 1.7996281748$$

$$R_0 \approx 1.8$$

Now that R_0 is greater than one ($R_0 > 1$) the disease became pandemic and therefore, spread quickly within the population, having contacts with the infected individuals. This results into an emergency respond that leads to the formulation of different mathematical modelling techniques to tackle and contain the epidemics of this kind.

Comparison With Real Data

The above model shows that the disease or pandemic started with the single case and speeded with highest peak of death cases of up to 10% of the population. It is being clearly seen when we compare the modelled influenza disease using Euler method in figure 1 above, which has about 10% peak of infection before it is eradicated after 100 days. Similarly, it can be seen from the real data of mortality from pandemic A/H1N1, 2009 influenza England: public surveillance study. The pandemic started with a single case from 1st June and went on to spread with highest peak of cases of up to 810,000 around the middle of July before the pandemic disappeared around the middle of September which is similar to the one model above in figure1 by applying Euler technique but the below chart of weekly estimated incidence of pandemic A/H1N1 2009 cases and confirmed deaths in England it is eight times of the modelled one which shows clearly about 10% highest peak when compared with other one modelled using the Euler method.

Fig 1 | Weekly estimated incidence of pandemic A/H1N1 cases (mid-range estimates) and confirmed deaths in England (source: Health Protection Agency)

Figure 2

Source: Donaldson *et al.*,(2009)

CONCLUSION

We modelled influenza virus using Euler techniques which follows SEIR Model and the model corresponds to the world problem which was modelled by different modelling techniques. The result shows clear similarities with the techniques or method adopted in the modelling of influenza virus by other researchers. We found out that Pandemic of the 21st century is considerably less lethal than was feared in advance case of fatality rate. Fatality has differ by age in a similar pattern of the previous pandemics. The research, shows that influenza can be modelled by SEIR model using Euler techniques, because in this piece of work, we found out that infectious cases reach it final peak of 10% within one hundred days before the disease disappeared or eradicated after hundreds days which is resemblance of the one obtained in weekly estimated incidence of pandemics AH1N1in figure 2. Similarly, the pandemics started with a single case as it can be seeing in the original graph of weekly estimated incident of pandemics A/H1N1 in Figure 2., which is an evidence that Euler techniques can be adopted to contained the pandemics of influenza virus with initial infectious case as one and more than 78% of the infected recovered as it was clearly seeing in the figure 1.

STRENGTH AND WEAKNESS

This work has a limitation to the use of SEIR model in modelling influenza virus using Euler techniques only, it fails to address any other model and techniques or disease. The feature work should focus on extension of this research work to the model that include vaccination that is to model influenza virus with vaccine. However, other method like Runge-Kutta can also be used in modelling the influenza virus.

REFERENCES

- Althaus, C.L. 2014, "Estimating the reproduction number of Ebola virus (EBOV) during the 2014 outbreak in West Africa", *PLoS currents*, vol. 6. Calisher C.H. 2009, "Swine flu", *Croat Medical*, 2009; 50:421-5. doi:10.3325/cmj.2009.50.412.
- Coburn, B.J., Wagner, B.G. & Blower, S. 2009, "Modelling influenza epidemics and pandemics: Insight in to the future of swine flu (H1N1)", *BMC Medical*, Available at: <http://www.biomedcentral.com/1741-7015/7/30>. 7:30 doi: 10.1186/1741-7015-7-30.

- Chowell, G., Ammon, C.E., Hangertner, N.W., & Hyman, J.M. 2006, "Estimation of the reproductive number of the Spanish flu epidemic in Geneva, Switzerland", Available online at: <http://www.elsevier.com/locate/vaccine>. 24 (2006) 6747-6750.
- Chowell, G., Ammon, C.E., Hangertner, N.W. & Hyman, J.M. 2006, "Transmission dynamics of great influenza pandemic of 1918 in Geneva Switzerland: Assessing the effects of hypothetical intervention", *Journal of Theoretical Biology*, Available online at: <http://www.elsevier.com/locate/yjtbi>. 241(2006)193-204.
- Donaldson, L.J., Rutter, P.D., Ellis, B.M., Greaves, F.E.C., Mytton, O.T., Pebody, R.G. & Yardley, L.E. 2009, "Mortality from pandemic A/H1N1 2009 influenza in England: Public health surveillance study", *BMJ* 2009; 339:65213.doi: 10.1136/bmj.b5213. Ear, S. 2012, "Mexico's handling of A/H1N1 in comparative perspective" emerging infectious disease (EIDs)", *Political economy disease control*, vol. 31, no. 1-2.
- Hattaf, K., & Yousif, N., "Mathematical Model of the influenza A/H1N1 Infection", *Advance Studies in Biology*, Vol.1, 2009.no. 8,383-390. Louz, D., Bergmans, H.E., Loos, B.P. & Hoeben, R.C. 2010, "Emergence of viral diseases: mathematical modelling as a tool for infection control, policy and decision making", *Critical reviews in microbiology*, vol. 36, no. 3, pp. 195- 211.
- Maher, B.J., & Butler, D. 2009, "One killer virus, three key question", *As the world mobilizes against the H1N1 flu pandemic*, Nature, & vol. 462.
- Newing, H., Eagle, C.M., Puri, R., Watson, C.W., 2011, "Conducting research in conservation: social science method and practice", *Routledge*, London, New York.
- Rose, M.A., Damm, O., Greiner, W., Knul, M., Wutzler, P., Liese, J.G., Kruger, H., Wahn, U., Schaberg, T., Schwehm, M., Kochmann, T. & Eichner, M. 2014, "The epidemiological impact of childhood influenza vaccination using live- attenuated influenza vaccine (LIAV) in Germany: Prediction of a simulation study", *BMC infectious disease*, 2014; Available at: <http://www.biomedcentral.com/1471-2334/14/40>.
- Sezena, R.K., Tripathi, P., Rawat, G. 2012, "Pandemism of swine flu and it prospective drug therapy", *Euro journal Clinical Microbiology Infectious Disease* 31:3265-3279. doi 1007/s 10096-021-1716-5.
- Shil, P., Gurav, Y.G., Chadha, M.S. & Mishra, A.C., 2009, "Transmission dynamics of influenza A/N1N1 2009 outbreak in a residential school in India", *Current science*, vol. 100 no. 8.